

Why Cox's Bazar Faces Load Shedding Despite Having 1,286 MW Generation Capacity: A Technical Analysis

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Abstract—Cox's Bazar is one of the important districts from the perspectives of economic contribution as well as tourism in Bangladesh, although electricity supply is a major problem in this area. It sounds somewhat paradoxical as the aggregate installed electricity generation capacity of plants in the district equals around 1,286 MW per day, which is much greater than the local demand of 200 MW per day. The study revealed that the main problem was not related to generation capacities but rather associated with the problems of the transmission network, voltage differences and the organization of the distribution grid. Specifically, the Matarbari coal power plant producing 1,200 MW is located in Cox's Bazar district. Its output is fed directly into the national grid.

Keywords—load shedding, Cox's Bazar, Matarbari coal power plant, voltage incompatibility, Bangladesh National Grid.

I. Introduction

Recognized globally as the location of the world's longest uninterrupted natural sea beach, Cox's Bazar is one of the most popular tourist attractions of Bangladesh. which receives millions of visitors annually. Apart from its tourism activities, the district economy is comprised of a vibrant fishing sector, widespread salt farming and many other business and service activities. [1] Therefore, electricity is crucial for all businesses and public utilities in addition to tourists' comfort. [2, 3]

However, it appears that the district is regularly subjected to power cuts. In fact, the district has such energy production facilities as the 1,200 MW Matarbari Coal-Fired Power Plant [4], the 20 MW Teknaf Solar Power Plant [5] and the 66 MW Cox's Bazar Wind Power Project [6] producing the total capacity of 1,286 MW which is almost seven times the daily demand of 200 MW. This paper explores why this substantial generation capacity fails to translate into reliable electricity supply.

II. Methodology

This research utilized primary and secondary sources for the research process. The primary source included institutional information collected from the Cox's Bazar office of Power Grid Company Bangladesh (PGCB), operational details from the Bangladesh Power Development Board (BPDB) and reports on the electricity sector available in public [7, 8].

For the secondary data collection, site visits were made to the Matarbari Power Plant, Teknaf Solar Power Plant, Cox's Bazar Wind Power Project, Matarbari 400 kV Substation and Cox's Bazar 132/33 kV Grid Substation. The knowledge gained from the observation of these fields was used in combination with technical and organizational information to create a holistic understanding of how generation, transmission and local distribution operate and fail. Field observations along with technical information were used to establish a full comprehension of how the system fails.

III. Results and Discussion

The findings indicate that load shedding problems in Cox's Bazar cannot be due to any shortage in electricity production within the region itself. Rather, this has something to do with the way the transmission network is designed. The Matarbari Power Plant transmits its electricity production using a 400 kV high-voltage network tied to the national grid. while the substation at Cox's Bazar runs in 132/33 kV voltage.

Figure 1. Cox's Bazar and Matarbari Grid Network. [9]

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the Matarbari Coal-Fired Power Plant operates at a transmission voltage of 400 kV; however, its substation infrastructure maintains no direct interconnection with the Cox's Bazar regional substation, which operates at 132/33 kV. Instead, the Cox's Bazar substation receives its feeders exclusively from the Teknaf Solar Power Plant and the Cox's Bazar Wind Power Project. Both have comparatively limited installed capacity.

Figure 2. Cox's Bazar and Matarbari Transmission Network SLD of the region. [10]

The SLD in Fig. 2 substantiates this configuration: the Matarbari substation feeds directly into the national grid with no dedicated feeder established toward the Cox's Bazar load center.

This presents an inherent technical problem in the sense that there are no appropriate transformer systems to reduce 400 kV electricity down to 132/33 kV. The plant cannot transmit its electricity directly into the local system of the region. Consequently all of its electricity is transmitted through the national grid according to national priority. There is no assurance of local allocation [7, 8]. While the Teknaf solar plant and Cox's Bazar wind power plant transmit electricity into the local grid. A total of 86 MW from both plants is far from meeting the daily requirement of 200 MW. The primary reasons are thus limitations on transmission design and incompatible voltages of generators and distributors. There is no direct channel for delivering electricity from the main generator to its final consumer.

IV. Recommendations

To address the underlying causes of load shedding and establish a reliable power supply in Cox's Bazar, the following measures are recommended:

1. Upgrade the Cox's Bazar 132/33 kV grid substation to handle higher-capacity transmission requirements.
2. Construct a dedicated high-voltage transmission line directly linking the Matarbari Substation with the Cox's Bazar Grid Substation.
3. Deploy high-capacity step-down transformers capable of converting 400 kV output from Matarbari to 132 kV or 33 kV, making it compatible with the local distribution network.

4. Development of regulation on priority allocation in Cox's Bazar through amendment of the present national grid dispatch protocol to include Cox's Bazar in the category of priority load zones. Such regulation will need to incorporate a consensus among BERC, PGCB and BPDB regarding power reservation contracts guaranteeing the minimum generation supplied from the national pool at times of high demand.

V. Conclusion

Even though the district of Cox's Bazar has 1,286 MW of generation capacity installed. There is a problem of load shedding due to the fact that the 1,200 MW capacity Matarbari Power Station is not yet connected to the local distribution network and the power generated by the plant feeds into the national grid at 400 kV level. while the local distribution network works on a voltage of 132/33kV, A strategic plan for substation development will solve this issue and facilitate economic growth in the tourism and fisheries sectors.

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